

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article discussed about the importance of creative methods in teaching foreign languages in primary schools and given some important information about it

There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our country, which today is striving to take its rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with foreign partners. «Start foreign languages, mainly English. To teach them from the third grade onwards, to increase their interest in teaching foreign languages, to teach English lessons in all secondary schools from the 1st grade in the form of various fun games, and at the same time the development of oral speech as well, and from the 2nd grade onwards, the transition to modern, innovative methods of teaching the alphabet, reading and grammar has begun gradually. Recently, the number of people of all ages learning English The reason for this is that it is becoming more and more difficult to live without knowing English in the course of life. But language learning also depends on the age. Even scientists children have proven to learn language faster and easier than adults. The

natural tendency of children to learn a language is due to the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, children spend more time than adults and memorize the information they learn quickly. As one of the Chinese inventors, Masaru Ibuka, wrote in his famous book, "Too Late After Us," "... a child's brain can have an infinite amount of information ...". It should also be noted that children aged 6-7 years do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. That is why it is important not to start teaching grammar to elementary school students who are learning English. Otherwise, the first step in learning a foreign language can be tiring for the child and weaken his or her interest in learning the language. Because it is difficult to teach a foreign language to primary school students, it is also one of the responsible tasks. Therefore, the following innovative methods can be used to teach English to primary school students in a meaningful and interesting way. Remember by sight.

It is known that young children remember the objects they see more than the information they hear. Therefore, the lesson is taught through a variety of visual aids, posters, something visible and often used in everyday life, teaching new words by writing on objects and composing sentences with the participation of new words learned. For example, writing a book, a table, a blackboard, a pen, a window, and so on. Because such items, which are often used in daily life, are constantly in sight and in constant use, the child learns these words involuntarily.

- Sing and compose words that are difficult to understand or remember through music. In addition to memorizing new words, the child's oral speech also develops.

For example, it can be shown that children's learning of the English alphabet by singing is more effective than just memorizing.

- TO includes most of the games that help you master competitive grammar and vocabulary. In doing so, the children perform a variety of tasks given by the teacher. As a result, there is competition among students and their interest in language learning increases. Indeed, as Chinese thinkers have said, «All human interests are created through competition.»

- Mixed technique where we can voluntarily combine different techniques. For example, children can play games, sing songs, draw pictures, and demonstrate new words through a variety of actions. The advantage of the technique is in the variety.

In doing so, the reader is not limited to just one thing.

- Teaching through cartoons. It is known that children are interested in watching different cartoons. In the process of watching cartoons in English, he tries to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters, even though he does not understand the words in the cartoon. This is a fun and effective way for children to learn the language.

Before exploring this new method, one should cite the views of a practicing psychologist: it should even try to involve the sense of smell and taste in the process of remembering.”

In fact, language learning through sensory organs is more useful and effective than other methods. For example, in the process of tasting an apple, the student knows what its color, taste, size, smell is, and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children the English name of the colors, the children immediately remember when they ate the fruit. Hence, the use of such methods helps the student to store the information in the memory for a long time.

In short, teaching language to primary school students not as an obligation, but rather through the use of fun games and innovative methods, can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, while the education system also has the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we, the future teachers, will be able to develop their own ways of effective use of innovative technologies. We can contribute.

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